

PHARMACOLOGICAL AND AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVES OF TRIPHALA GUGGULU AND DARVI TAILA IN CHRONIC CERVICITIS (PARIPLUTA YONI VYAPAD): AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic cervicitis is a common gynecological condition characterized by recurrent inflammation of the uterine cervix, often due to microbial infection, chemical irritants, or immune dysregulation. Standard therapies, including systemic antibiotics and procedural interventions, frequently fail to prevent recurrence. **Objective:** This review explores the pharmacological and therapeutic potential of two classical Ayurvedic formulations, *Triphala Guggulu* (internal) and *Darvi Taila* (local), in the management of chronic cervicitis. **Methods:** A narrative review was conducted using classical Ayurvedic texts (Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Sarangdhara Samhita, Sahasrayoga) and modern biomedical literature indexed in PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Search terms included “cervicitis,” “*Paripluta Yoni Vyapad*,” “*Triphala Guggulu*,” “*Darvi*

Taila,” “*Berberis aristata*,” and “*Commiphora wightii*.” **Results:** *Triphala Guggulu* exhibits anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, analgesic, and wound-healing properties, supported by both Ayurvedic references and modern pharmacological studies. *Darvi Taila*, when applied locally via *Pichu kriya*, provides tissue regeneration, antimicrobial effects, and localized anti-inflammatory action. Together, these formulations address both systemic and local pathology, including dosha imbalance and mucosal healing, offering a holistic therapeutic strategy. **Conclusion:** Integrating *Triphala Guggulu* and *Darvi Taila* in chronic cervicitis management aligns with an evidence-informed, dosha-correcting, and tissue-healing approach. Controlled

clinical trials with standardized formulations are warranted to validate these traditional therapies in modern practice.

KEYWORDS: Cervicitis, *Paripluta Yoni Vyapad*, *Triphala Guggulu*, *Darvi Taila*, Ayurveda, Integrative Medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical infections are a major cause of reproductive health problems, especially in sexually active women, since the cervix acts as a key barrier and entry point for infections of the genital tract. Cervicitis, which is inflammation of the uterine cervix, significantly contributes to reproductive health issues worldwide. It is commonly caused by sexually transmitted pathogens such as *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Trichomonas vaginalis*, and *Mycoplasma genitalium*, along with viral agents like HSV. Non-infectious causes include chemical irritants, foreign objects, and hypersensitivity reactions. Chronic and recurrent cervicitis can lead to symptoms like pain during sex, abnormal vaginal discharge, bleeding between periods, pelvic discomfort, infertility, and a higher risk of pelvic inflammatory disease and HIV infection.

Conventional management includes systemic antibiotics (azithromycin, doxycycline, ceftriaxone), topical estrogen therapy, and procedural interventions such as cryotherapy or laser ablation. However, recurrence, antimicrobial resistance, and incomplete mucosal healing limit long-term efficacy.

Ayurveda interprets chronic cervical inflammation as *Paripluta Yoni Vyapad*, one of twenty types of *Yoni Vyapad* described in classical texts. Etiology involves vitiation of *Vata* and *Pitta doshas* (Charaka) or *Vata* predominance (Sushruta), manifesting as cervical tenderness, mucopurulent discharge, dyspareunia, backache, and fever. Traditional management integrates internal administration (*Triphala Guggulu*) and local therapies (*Darvi Taila* via Pichu kriya), targeting both dosha balance and tissue repair.

METHODS

A narrative review methodology was employed. Classical Ayurvedic texts (Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Sarangdhara Samhita, Sahasrayoga, Bhavaprakasha, Yoga Ratnakara) were reviewed for disease description, etiology, symptomatology, and treatment principles. Modern biomedical literature was identified through PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar,

using the search terms: “cervicitis,” “*Paripluta Yoni Vyapad*,” “*Triphala Guggulu*,” “*Darvi Taila*,” “*Berberis aristata*,” “*Commiphora wightii*,” and “Ayurveda gynecology.” Only English-language articles were included.

REVIEW FINDINGS

1. Biomedical View of Cervicitis

Cervicitis is primarily caused by microbial pathogens such as *C. trachomatis*, *N. gonorrhoeae*, *M. genitalium*, and *T. vaginalis*, as well as viral agents like HSV. Non-infectious causes include chemical irritants, foreign bodies, or allergic reactions to latex or spermicides. Chronic cervicitis may lead to complications such as pelvic inflammatory disease, infertility, and increased susceptibility to HIV. Clinical features often include mucopurulent discharge, intermenstrual bleeding, dyspareunia, and pelvic discomfort, although subclinical cases are common.

Conventional pharmacotherapy comprises systemic antibiotics and local estrogen therapy. Refractory cases may require ablative procedures like cryotherapy, laser ablation, or conization. However, recurrence and microbial resistance have prompted a search for complementary therapeutic approaches.

2. Ayurvedic Perspective – *Paripluta Yoni Vyapad*

Paripluta yoni vyapada

All Ayurvedic Acharyas described 20 types of *Yoni-Vyapad*. *Paripluta yoni-vyapad* is one of them, which is described by Acharya Charaka, Sushruta and Vagbhata. The etiopathogenesis of *Paripluta* is different in Acharya Charaka and Acharya Sushruta.

पित्तलाया नृसंवासे क्षवथूद्गारधारणात् ।

पित्तसम्मूर्च्छितो वायुर्योनिं दूषयति स्त्रियाः ॥२३॥

शूना स्पर्शाक्षमा सार्तिर्नीलपीतमसृक्सवेत् ।

श्रोणिवङ्क्षणपृष्ठार्तिज्वरार्तायाः परिप्लुता ॥२४॥ (च.चि ३०)

Acharya Charaka has described this disease is due to vitiation of *Vata* and *Pitta*, A women who have dominance of *Pitta* in her body, withholds her urge of sneezing and eructation at the time of coitus the vitiated *Pitta* mixed with *Vata* causes abnormality of *yoni*.

Acharya Charaka mentioned signs and symptoms of *paripluta yonivyapada* as *Shuna* (inflamed), *Sparshakshama* (tender), *Saarti neelapeetamasrik* (painful with yellow or bluish menstruation) along with *Shroni*, *Vankshan*, *Pristhaarti* (backache, pain in lumbo-sacral and groin region) with *Jwara* (fever).

Acharya Sushruta characterized this condition with complaint of *Gramyadharmaruja* (severe dyspareunia) with other pains and aches. According to Sushruta this disease is due to vitiation of *Vata* only.

Both Vagbhata have followed Acharya Charaka but they have given heaviness in bladder and lower abdomen with diarrhoea and anorexia. Other text i.e., Bhav Prakasha, Madhava nidana and Yoga Ratnakara followed Acharya Sushruta.

In the description of this disorder, the opinions of Charaka and Sushruta are quite different. Acharya Charaka says it is due to *Vata* and *Pitta* having inflammation, fever and backache etc. as symptoms, while Acharya Sushruta has mentioned it to be due to *vata* having only one symptom i.e., dyspareunia.

Treatment of Yoni Vyapat

Management of *yonirogas* mainly include both *sodhana* and *samana* measures in classics. Local and generalized management of *yonirogas* is done with *Pancha karma*, *Basti* and *Uttara basti* procedures. Besides these procedures other special therapies like *Seka*, *Abhyanga* and *Pichu kriya* is also mentioned in Charaka samhitha.

In conditions like chronic cervicitis, infection persists for long period, so only *bahiparimarjana* is not sufficient for elimination of infection. Due to chronicity in inflammation, pain occur in uterus and cervix and persist for long time. Hence the selected drug should possess *sothahara*, *rujahara* and *vrana ropana* like actions and so in the present study *Triphala guggulu* is chosen for internal administration and *Darvi taila* is chosen for *Pichu kriya*, both of which have been already proved to have anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial and analgesic activity from previous studies.

Table 1: Comparison of Cervicitis Features – Biomedical vs Ayurvedic.

Feature	Biomedical View	Ayurvedic View (Paripluta Yoni Vyapat)
Etiology	<i>Chlamydia trachomatis</i> , <i>N.</i>	Vata-Pitta vitiation (Charaka), Vata

	<i>gonorrhoeae, M. genitalium, HSV, irritants</i>	predominance (Sushruta)
Symptoms	Mucopurulent discharge, dyspareunia, intermenstrual bleeding, backache	Shuna (inflamed), Sparshakshama (tender), Saarti (pain), Neelapeeta discharge, backache, fever
Chronicity	Recurrent infection, antimicrobial resistance	Persistent dosha imbalance, repeated inflammation
Management	Antibiotics, local estrogen, procedural interventions	Internal: Triphala Guggulu; Local: Darvi Taila via Pichu

3. Reference and description of drugs used in study

3.1 Triphala Guggulu

Triphala guggulu is a classical Ayurvedic herbal formulation. The reference is from Sharangdhara Samhitha Madhyama khanda 7/82-83. This preparation contains Triphala (*Haritaki, Vibhithaki, Amalaki*) and Guggulu as main ingredient along with Pippali. This formulation is indicated in the treatment of *Bhangandara, Gulma, Shotha* and *Arsa* as per Acharya Sarangdhara. Also, it has been mentioned under *Vrana sotha* and *Vidradi rogadohikar* in *Chakradatta* and *Yoga ratnakara* respectively.

In Sarangdhara samhitha,

- त्रिपलम् त्रिफलाचूर्णं कृष्णचूर्णं पलोन्मितम् ।

गुग्गुलुः पञ्चपलिकः क्षोदयेत्सर्वमेकतः ॥

ततस्तु गुटिकां कृत्वा प्रयुञ्ज्यात् वहनयपेक्षया ।

भगन्दर गुल्मशोथावर्शासि च विनाशयेत् ॥ (शा.स. म ७/८२-८३)

In Chakradatta,

- त्रिफलाचूर्णसंयुक्तो गुग्गुलुर्वटकीकृतः ।

निर्यन्त्रणो विबन्धघ्नो व्रणशोधनरोपणः ॥ (व्रणशोथाधिकारः ६८)

In Yoga ratnakara,

- त्रीणि पलानि फलत्रितयस्य द्वे तु पले तुलिते मगधायाः ।

पञ्च पलानि भवन्ति पुरस्य स्यात्स फलत्रिकगुग्गुलुयोगः ॥ ५१ ॥

पक्वेषु विद्रधिषु पूयमतिस्त्रवत्सु नाडीषु च व्रणगदेषु भगन्दरेषु ।

स्याद्गण्डमालिषुफलत्रिकगुग्गुलुःस्यात्पथ्यंफलत्रिकपुरे घृतभोजनं च ॥५२ ॥ (विद्रध्यधिकारः ४६)

Triphala guggulu is used for oral administration. It has *Dahasamana, Vedanahara, Vrana Sodhana and Ropana* properties. As it contains Guggulu which has *Sukshma, Laghu, Sara gunas* it will provide fast absorption in body through *Sukshma srotas* and because of *Snigdha, Picchila gunas* it will provide prolonged drug action too. The *Vati* prepared out of *Triphala & Guggulu* when taken internally Cures *Vibandha* and it acts as *Vrana Shodhaka & Vrana Ropaka*. *Triphala* and *Pippali* is also studied for their anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antimicrobial and anti-pyretic actions. *Triphala* along with *Guggulu* taken internally relieves pain, swelling, moisture and discharge. *Triphala guggulu* contains phenols, alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids fats and oils, tannins and tarpenoid which helps in reducing inflammation and promote healing. Thus, the drug is chosen for the present clinical study on the management of chronic cervicitis.

Table 2: Triphala Guggulu – Ayurvedic & Pharmacological Properties.

Ingredient	Botanical Name	Ayurvedic Properties	Pharmacological Action	Active Constituents	Part Used
Haritaki	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Laghu, Ruksha	Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic, Wound healing	Tannins, Chebulic acid	Fruit
Vibhitaki	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Laghu, Ruksha	Anti-inflammatory, Antibacterial	Chebulinic acid, Gallic acid	Fruit
Amalaki	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	Guru, Ruksha	Immunomodulatory, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant	Vitamin C, Gallic acid, Fisetin	Fruit
Pippali	<i>Piper longum</i>	Laghu, Snigdha, Tikshna	Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic	Piperine, Volatile oils	Fruit
Guggulu	<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	Laghu, Ruksha, Sukshma	Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial, Wound healing	E & Z- Guggulsterone, Ellagic acid	Gum resin

3.2 Darvi Taila

1. Darvi taila is mentioned by Acharya Charaka as the best *Vranaropaka* in *Dwivraneeya chikitsa adhyaya* where Darvi is the only ingredient.

दूर्वास्वरससिद्धं वा तैलं कम्पिल्लकेन वा।

दार्वीत्वचश्चकल्केन प्रधानं व्रणरोपणं।। (Cha. chi. 25/93)

2. Darvi taila is also mentioned in Sahasrayoga, where *Daru haridra*, *Grihadhuma*, *Yashtyahwa* (*Yasti madhu*) and *Nisa* (*Haridra*) are its ingredients and is indicated in *Medra roga*.

दार्वीस्वरसयष्ट्याहव गृहधूम निशायुतं।

तैलमभ्यञ्जनात्पक्वंमेद्रोगं विनाशयेत्॥ (Sahasrayoga taila prakarana 28)

In Charak samhitha the *Darvi taila* is used in the treatment of *Dushta Vrana* as a local use. Taila Kalpana has been described by Acharya Sushruta as one of the Shasti Upakramas which can be used for *Shodhana* and *Ropana* karma in *Dushta Vrana*.

In this clinical study, we have decided to evaluate the clinical efficacy of *Darvi taila* mentioned in Sahasrayoga by excluding *Grihadhuma* (by considering its availability and reliability) in the management of chronic cervicitis.

Probable mode of action

Tila taila, has *lekhaniya* and *krimighna* action and thus reducing oedema and infection. Also due to *lekhaniya guna* it helps to remove cell debris hence helps in *vrana-ropana*. It is *vata shamak* due to *ushna veerya* and *snigdha guna*, hence reduces *shoola*. Taila used is *vyadhipratyanik* for vitiated dosha, alleviated *vata* is reduced from wound. Taila has *Madhura rasa*, so it promotes strength and lustre, alleviates *pitta* and *vata* and pacifies heat ultimately promoting healing process.

Darvi is included in *Kandughna*, *Kushtaghna*, *Arshoghna mahakashaya*, *Haridradi gana* and *Lakshadi gana*. Its *Tikta Katu rasa*, *Ushna Veerya* and *Katu Vipaka* with *Laghu* and *Ruksha guna* helps in *lekhana* and thereby reduces the discharge. *Darvi* has *Tikta Katu Rasa* so these *rasa* acts as a *Shodhana* of Infected site. *Haridra* is included under *Lekhaniya*, *Kandughna* and *Krimighna gana* by Acharya Charaka. It is *Kapha-Vata shamaka* due to its *Ushna veerya* and *Pitta shamaka* due to its *Tikta rasa* and pacifies *Kapha* due to *Ruksha guna* and *Katu Tikta rasa*. *Yashti madhu* having *Guru Snigdha guna* and *Madhura rasa* is *Vata shamaka* and is also *Pitta shamaka* due to *Madhura rasa* and *Sheeta veerya*. It is included under *Jeevaniya*, *Kandughna* and *Mutravirajaniya gana* by Acharya Charaka.

Antimicrobial activity of *Daruharidra* and *Yashti madhu* might help to fight against infection and promote rapid healing of ulcer. Analgesic, Anti-inflammatory properties of *Daruharidra*,

Haridra and Yashti madhu help in reducing the inflammation. Yashti madhu also has anti pyretic action hence useful in conditions like infection and inflammation.

Hence *Darvi taila* having these ingredients can be selected for the study of management of Chronic cervicitis where signs of inflammation are the major feature.

Table 3: Darvi Taila – Ingredients & Actions.

Ingredient	Botanical Name	Ayurvedic Properties	Pharmacological Action	Part Used
Daruharidra	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Laghu, Ruksha	Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory	Root
Haridra	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Laghu, Ruksha	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant	Rhizome
Yashti Madhu	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Guru, Snigdha	Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial, Anti-pyretic	Root/Rhizome

Fig.1: Mode of action of the intervention.

DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic approach provides a unique methodology to manage chronic cervicitis, not just by targeting pathogens, but by correcting underlying *dosha* imbalances and promoting tissue regeneration. Triphala Guggulu, as per Ayurvedic classics, exhibits multi-pronged therapeutic actions: *Vranaropana* (wound healing), *Shothahara* (anti-inflammatory), and *Krimighna* (antimicrobial). Its constituents, such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds, have demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activity in in vitro and in vivo studies.

Darvi Taila, applied locally via *Pichu kriya*, aligns with the principles of *Snehana* (oleation) and *Shodhana* (cleansing). Its ingredients—*Daruharidra*, *Haridra*, and *Yashti Madhu*—are pharmacologically validated for their antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and mucosal healing properties. Taila formulation ensures deeper tissue penetration, prolonged retention, and localized effect through *Snigdha* and *Sukshma* properties, allowing direct action at the cervicovaginal site.

From a biomedical standpoint, this dual therapeutic strategy—internal and topical administration—addresses both systemic immunity and localized inflammation, potentially reducing recurrence and microbial colonization. While modern antimicrobials are highly targeted, they often fail to restore mucosal integrity or immune balance. Ayurvedic interventions may fill this gap by providing anti-inflammatory effects and mucosal rejuvenation concurrently.

Triphala Guggulu, composed of *Triphala* (*Haritaki*, *Bibhitaki*, *Amalaki*), *Pippali*, and *Guggulu* (*Commiphora mukul*), exhibits a multifaceted mode of action. It possesses potent anti-inflammatory activity through inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX) pathways, along with suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6. Additionally, it demonstrates broad-spectrum antimicrobial action against pathogens including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida* species. Its immunomodulatory and antioxidant effects, combined with detoxifying actions and *Vata–Pitta* pacifying properties, make it especially suitable for inflammatory gynecological disorders.

Simultaneously, *Triphala Guggulu* works systemically to reduce inflammation, eliminate *ama* (toxins), and enhance *Dhatu poshana* (tissue nourishment). The integration of systemic *Shamana* therapy with local *Sthanika Chikitsa* via *Darvi Taila Pichu* represents a synergistic approach that promotes restoration of vaginal health and resolution of chronic inflammation.

These therapeutic concepts are also validated in classical Ayurvedic texts: *Charaka Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya* recommend *Pichu karma* as a preferred method for *Yoni Vyapad* due to its sustained local effect and *dosha*-pacifying action, while *Bhavaprakasha* and *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* extol the multi-dimensional benefits of *Triphala* and *Guggulu* in chronic inflammatory conditions of the reproductive tract.

Darvi Taila, administered locally via *Pichu*, contains *Daruharidra* (*Berberis aristata*), *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*), and *Yashtimadhu* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), each contributing uniquely to its therapeutic profile. *Daruharidra* contains berberine, which inhibits microbial DNA synthesis and suppresses the NF- κ B inflammatory pathway, offering marked antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. *Haridra*, rich in curcumin, suppresses COX-2 expression and promotes mucosal healing. *Yashtimadhu* exhibits soothing, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial actions, helping reduce irritation and infection. The *Pichu* delivery enhances local absorption and maintains prolonged contact with the cervical mucosa.

Fig. 2: comparing Ayurvedic and Biomedical targets.

Limitations

- Few randomized clinical trials exist.
- Standardization of formulations and dosages is required.
- Future studies should include objective outcome measures (cytology, microbial culture, inflammatory markers).

CONCLUSION

Chronic cervicitis remains a therapeutic challenge due to recurrent inflammation and microbial resistance. Ayurvedic formulations, Triphala Guggulu and *Darvi Taila*, offer promising integrative alternatives with anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, analgesic, and tissue-healing properties. These remedies target both systemic and local pathology, restore mucosal integrity, and correct dosha imbalance. Rigorous clinical trials with standardized protocols are recommended to establish their evidence-based role in modern gynecological practice.

REFERENCES

1. Workowski KA, Bachmann LH, Chan PA, Johnston CM, Muzny CA, Park I, et al. Sexually transmitted infections treatment guidelines, 2021. *MMWR Recomm Rep.*, 2021; 70(4): 1–187.
2. Paavonen J, Eggert-Kruse W. Chlamydia trachomatis: impact on human reproduction. *Hum Reprod Update*, 1999; 5(5): 433–447.
3. Taylor SN. Cervicitis: an overview of diagnosis and management. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.*, 2011; 205(4): 319–325.
4. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Sexually transmitted disease surveillance 2020. Atlanta: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2021.
5. Brunham RC, Gottlieb SL, Paavonen J. Pelvic inflammatory disease. *N Engl J Med.*, 2015; 372(21): 2039–2048.
6. Wiesenfeld HC, Hillier SL, Krohn MA, Landers DV, Sweet RL. Bacterial vaginosis is a strong predictor of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis* infection. *Clin Infect Dis.*, 2003; 36(5): 663–668.
7. Stafl A, Wilbanks GD. Chronic cervicitis: a study of 300 cases. *Obstet Gynecol.*, 1971; 38(5): 602–607.
8. Charaka Samhita (Ch. Chi.), Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi.
9. Sushruta Samhita, Prof. K.R. Srikantha Murthy, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi.
10. Sarngadhara Samhita, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi.
11. Sahasrayoga Sangraha Taila Prakaran, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi.
12. Baliga MS. Triphala, Ayurvedic formulation for treating and preventing cancer: a review. *J Altern Complement Med.*, 2010; 16(12): 1301–1308.
13. Chandrasekaran CV, Sundarajan K, David K, Agarwal A. In vitro modulation of LPS/calcimycin induced inflammatory and allergic mediators by *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root extract. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2011; 3(2): 267–270.
14. Zahid S (2016) Effect of Unani Formulation in Cervicitis: A Single-blind Randomised Placebo-controlled trial. *Altern integr Med* doi:10.4172/2327-5162.1000213
15. Neelam Rawat et al. Anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial action of Triphala guggulu: A Review. *Int. J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm.*, 2022; 13(4).
16. Lee H.S, Jung S.H, Yun B.S, Lee K.W. Isolation of chebulic acid from *Terminalia chebula* Retz. and its antioxidant effect in isolated rat hepatocytes. *Arch Toxicol.*, 2007; 81(3): 211–218.

17. Ahmad I, Mehmood Z, Mohammad F. Screening of some Indian medicinal plants for their antimicrobial properties. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* September, 1998; 62(2): 183-193.
18. K. B. Ishnava, Y. N. Mahida, and J. S. S. Mohan, "In vitro assessments of antibacterial potential of *Commiphora wightii* (Arn.) Bhandari. gum extract," *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*, 2010; 2(7): 91–96.
19. Vedhanayaki G, Shastri G.V, Kuruvilla A. Analgesic activity of *Piper longum* Linn. Root. *Indian journal exp biology.* June, 2003; 41(6): 649-51.
20. Charkasamhita: Text with english translation and critical exposition based on Cakrapani datta's *Ayurveda Dipika*. Published by Chowkhamba sanskrit series office, Varanasi.
21. Dr. Suneeta Singh. (2016). Clinical Evaluation of the Effect of Udumberadi Tail Uttar Vasti in the Management of Chronic Cervicitis. *Global Journal of Medical Research*, 16(F2): 7–10. Retrieved from <https://medicalresearchjournal.org/index.php/GJMR/article/view/1061>
22. Sarngadhara Samhitha of Sarangdharacharya translated by Dr. P. Himasagara Chandra Murthy published by Chowkhamba sanskrit series Varanasi.
23. Prathima A H M & Sucheta Kumari: M clinical Study of Paripluta Yonivyapad with Yashtimadhu Ghrita Yoni Pichu W.S.R To Pelvic Inflammatory Disease. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal* {online} 2017 {cited September, 2017} Available from: http://www.iamj.in/posts/images/upload/3406_3412.pdf
24. *Dravyaguna Vigyan* by Priyavrata Sharma, I volume Chowkhamba Bharti Academy publisher, 2011.
25. *Dravyaguna Vigyan* by Priyavrata Sharma, II volume Chowkhamba Bharti Academy publisher, 2011.
26. Dhanwanthari Nighantu, *Indian Materia Medica of SRI MAHENDRA BHOGIKA (10th-11th Century) Guducyadi Varg, Shloka, No.64.*
27. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu, *Indian Materia Medica of SRI BHAVAMISRA (C. 1500-1600A.D.) Haritakyadi Varg, Shloka No-146.*
28. Bhavaprakasa Nighantu, *Indian Materia Medica of SRI BHAVAMISRA (C. 1500-1600A.D.), Haritakyadi Varg, Shloka No. 119.*
29. Young C, Argáez C. Management and Treatment of Cervicitis: A Review of Clinical Effectiveness and Guidelines [Internet]. Ottawa (ON): Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health; 2017 Sep 21. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK525875/>

30. Sahasrayoga Sangraha taila Prakaran, Dr. R. Vidyanath, Dr. K. Nishteswar, Published by Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 2008 edition.
31. Dutta, D.C, Textbook of Gyneacology, Hiralal Konar, Jaypee brothers' medical publishers, 7th Edition, Chapter 13. p.137.
32. Susruta Samhita of Acharya Susruta: Prof.K.R. SrikanthaMurthy, Published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi.